

Microfacies Analysis of Carbonate Rocks from Kawkalut Taung, Kyaikmaraw Township, Mon State

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Abstract

The studied area located in the southeastern part of Kyaikmaraw Township, Mon State within topographic maps number 94 H/11 and 94/15. The limestone outcrops have been observed in the form of Pillar-like hills majestically stuck out from alluviated land. The area is mainly consisted of Permian Moulmein limestone. The black limestone, dolomitic limestone, fossiliferous limestone and micritic limestone occur in the area. Microscopic analysis indicates that the rock types are peloidal bioclastic wackestone, bioclastic peloidal wackestone, bioclastic mudstone, oolitic peloidal wackestone, bioclastic peloidal packstone, dolomitic peloidal wackestone, oolitic peloidal packstone (microstylolite), peloidal packstone, bioclastic peloidal grainstone and intraclastic grainstone. Fossils included are bryozoans, gastropods, foraminiferas, echinoderms and other broken shell fragments. These limestones were deposited in the supratidal, intertidal and subtidal environments. From the study of microfacies and deposition environment, the area was a shallow marine platform environment. During the Permian period, the area was transgressed which was followed by minor transgressive and regressive cycles under different energy level. These rocks are suitable for cementing material.

Introduction

Location

The studied area located in the southeastern part of Kyaikmaraw Township, Mon State. It lies between Latitude 16° 20' to 16° 22' N and Longitude 97° 45' to 97° 47' E and is situated between horizontal grids no. 82 to 84 and vertical grids no. 36 to 39 in one inch topographic map sheet no. 94 H/11 and 94 H/ 15 of Myanmar Survey Department. Location map of the area is shown in (Fig.1).

Objectives

The detailed carbonate petrography, specific carbonate microfacies analysis and study of depositional environments are focused as principal objectives.

Methods of study

Field method - Detailed sedimentary facies measurements were carried out from traverse lines, representative sample collection and taking photographs were done wherever necessary. Laboratory method - 22 thin-sections were examined under polarizing microscope for detailed petrography and visual estimation of the constituent grains. The rocks of the study area can be divided into different microfacies types and interpret the possible depositional environments.

Carbonate Petrology

Limestones of Kawkalut taung can be classified into ten microfacies. These microfacies are (1) peloidal bioclastic wackestone, (2) bioclastic peloidal wackestone, (3) bioclastic mudstone (4) oolitic peloidal wackestone, (5) bioclastic peloidal packstone, (6) dolomitic peloidal wackestone, (7) oolitic peloidal packstone, (8) peloidal packstone, (9) bioclastic peloidal grainstone, and (10) intraclastic grainstone.

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Fig. (1) Location map of the study area.

Facies description

Petrographic characteristics and depositional environments of the Kawkalut Taung limestones are shown in (Fig. 2).

Microfacies-1: Peloidal bioclastic wackestone

At the exposure, the rock is grey colour on fresh surface and reddish grey on weathered surface. It is fine to medium-grained and massive nature. Under the microscope, it contains pellets and bioclasts 40-50%, micrite 20-30% and sparite 5-10% (Fig. 3). Gypsum minerals are found in this rock. The pellets are subrounded in shape. Micritization is occurred on the boundaries of bioclasts. The internal pores filled with calcite cement. Therefore, the rock can be called pel-bio micrite using Folk's classification (1959, 1962). According to Dunham (1962), it can be named as peloidal bioclastic wackestone.

Microfacies-2: Bioclastic peloidal wackestone

It is yellowish grey colour on fresh surface and dark grey on weathered surface. It is fine-grained and laminations. Under the microscope, it comprises bioclasts and peloids 40-50% and micrite 30-40% (Fig. 4). Dolomites present about 10-15%. Echinoderm and foraminifera are occurred in this rock. Syntaxial rinds occur on echinoderm. 10-15% of rhom shape dolomites are found in this facies. Therefore, this rock may be called bio-pel micrite (Folk, 1959, 1962) and bioclastic peloidal wackestone (Dunham, 1962).

Microfacies-3: Bioclastic mudstone

At the exposure, the rock is grey colour on fresh surface and black on weathered surface. It is fine-grained. Under the microscope, it contains micrite 80-90% and bioclasts 5-10% (Fig. 5). Some bioclasts are filled with calcite crystals. The silt sized terrigenous detritus (quartz) contains 0.1 to 2%. Therefore, this rock can be defined bio micrite (Folk, 1959, 1962) and bioclastic mudstone (Dunham, 1962).

Microfacies-4: Oolitic peloidal wackestone

The rock is black colour on both fresh and weathered surfaces. It is fine-grained and

Fig. (2) Petrographic characteristics and depositional environments of Kawkalut Taung limestones (Measured from 372830 to 375831)

parallel laminations. Under the microscope, it contains ooids 5-10%, peloids 30-40% and micrite 40-50% (Fig. 6). Ooids show concentric structure which have been partly lost by micritization. Various sizes of pellets are found in this rock. The rock may be designated as oolitic peloidal wackestone (Dunham, 1962).

Microfacies-5: Bioclastic peloidal packstone

At the exposure, the rocks are dark grey colour on fresh surface and black on weathered surface. It is fine to medium-grained and massive nature. Under the microscope, it contains bioclasts 10-15%, peloids 20-40%, sparites 20-30% and micrite 10-20% (Fig. 7). Some bioclasts are foraminifera. The peloids are fecal pellets and subrounded micritic grains of other origin. The rock can be named as bio-pel sparite (Folk, 1959, 1962). According to Dunham (1962), it can be named as bioclastic peloidal packstone.

Microfacies-6: Dolomitic peloidal wackestone

It is dark grey colour on both fresh and weathered surfaces. It is medium-grained and massive nature. Under the microscope, dolomites occur 40-50% of the total rock volume. They show subhedral to euhedral form. Some dolomite rhombs are cloudy and remain the ghost of the micrite (Fig. 8). Quartz particles occur as terrigenous input. Pellet grains occur about 20-30%. Micrite occurs as interstitial materials. The rock can be called as dolomitic pel micrite (Folk, 1959, 1962) and dolomitic peloidal wackestone (Dunham, 1962).

Microfacies-7: Oolitic peloidal packstone

It is dark grey colour on both fresh and weathered surfaces. It is fine to medium-grained and thick-bedded to massive nature. Under the microscope, it contains ooids 10-15%, peloids 40-60%, sparry calcite cement 20-30% and micrite 10-15% (Fig. 9). Microstylolite is found in this rock. The rock can be named as oo-pel sparite (Folk, 1959, 1962) and oolitic peloidal packstone (Dunham, 1962).

Microfacies-8: Peloidal packstone

It is fine to medium-grained and dark grey colour on both fresh and weathered surfaces. Under the microscope, it contains peloids 30-40%, micrite 10-20% and sparite 30-40%. Drusy mosaic of calcite cement exists as inside cavity (Fig. 10). The rock can be called as pel sparite using Folk's classification (1959, 1962). According to Dunham (1962), it can be called as peloidal packstone.

Microfacies-9: Bioclastic peloidal grainstone

It is light grey colour on fresh surface and dark grey on weathered surface. It is coarse-grained. Under the microscope, it contains bioclasts 10-20%, peloids 30-50% and sparite 30-40% (Fig. 11). The rock can be designated as bio-pel sparite (Folk, 1959, 1962) and bioclastic peloidal packstone (Dunham, 1962).

Microfacies-10: Intraclastic grainstone

It is light grey colour on fresh surface and black on weathered surface. It is medium-grained crystalline limestone. Under the microscope, it contains intraclasts 25% and peloids 40% (Fig. 12). The cementation is mainly composed of sparry calcite. The rock can be named as intra sparite (Folk, 1959, 1962) and intraclastic grainstone (Dunham, 1962).

Fig. (3) Pellets, bioclasts and sparite cement in intraskeletal cavity of gastropod (Under P.P.L).

Fig. (4) Bioclasts and terrigenous detritus in bioclastic peloidal wackestone (Between X.N).

Fig. (5) Bioclasts in bioclastic mudstone (Between X.N).

Fig. (6) Ooids and pellets in oolitic peloidal wackestone (Under P.P.L).

Fig. (7) Bioclasts and peloids in bioclastic peloidal packstone (Under P.P.L).

Fig. (8) Dolomite crystals in dolomitic peloidal wackestone (Between X.N).

Fig. (9) Pellets and sparite in oolitic peloidal packstone (Under P.P.L).

Fig. (10) Geopetal structure in peloidal packstone (Under P.P.L).

Fig. (11) Bioclasts and pellets cemented with sparry calcite in bioclastic peloidal grainstone (Under P.P.L)

Fig. (12) Intraclast in intraclastic grainstone (Under P.P.L).

Facies association and recognition of depositional environment

Three major depositional environments are identified on the basis of grain types, physical and biogenic sedimentary structures, and vertical facies relations. These include supratidal, intertidal and subtidal environments. These three environments are represented by 10 microfacies which are shown in table (1), (2), (3).

Table (1) Microfacies association and characteristic features of supratidal environment in Kawkalut Taung.

Microfacies	Characteristic features
Peloidal bioclastic wackestone (microfacies-1) Bioclastic mudstone (microfacies-3) Peloidal packstone (microfacies-8)	Gypsum, peloids, carbonate mud, bioclasts, low energy, content of silica, thick-bedded to massive.

Table (2) Microfacies association and characteristic features of intertidal environment in Kawkalut Taung. .

Microfacies	Characteristic features
Olitic peloidal wackstone (microfacies -4) Olitic peloidal packstone (microfacies-7) Peloidal packstone (microfacies-8) Bioclastic peloidal grainstone (microfacies -9) Intraclastic grainstone (microfacies -10)	Ooids, peloids, abundant bioclasts, minor amount of micrite, and mainly sparry calcite, moderate energy, thick-bedded to massive.

Table (3) Microfacies association and characteristic features of subtidal environment in Kawkalut Taung.

Microfacies	Characteristic features
Bioclastic peloidal wackstone (microfacies-2) Bioclastic peloidal packstone (microfacies -5) Dolomitic peloidal wackstone (microfacies -6) Intraclastic grainstone (microfacies-10)	Peloids, bioclasts, dolomicrosparite, dolomite, intraclasts, moderate energy, thick-bedded to massive.

Conclusion

It composes of carbonate rocks of Moulmein limestone in Permian age. Stratigraphically, it can be correlated with the plateau limestone. According to Folk's (1959, 1962) classification and Dunham's (1962) classification, limestones of Kawkalut Taung are classified ten microfacies. Peloidal bioclastic wackstone, bioclastic mudstone and peloidal packstone were deposited in supratidal environment. Oolitic peloidal wackstone, oolitic peloidal packstone, peloidal packstone and bioclastic peloidal grainstone and intraclastic grainstone were deposited in intertidal environment. Bioclastic peloidal wackstone, bioclastic peloidal packstone, dolomitic peloidal wackstone and intraclastic grainstone were deposited in subtidal environment. During the Permian, the area was transgressed which was followed by minor transgressive and regressive cycles under different energy level. These limestones are suitable for cementing material.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my thanks to Dr. Aye Aye Tun, Rector and Dr. Yin Yin Than, Pro-Rector, Bago University, for their permission to present this paper.

References

- Dunham, K.J. (1962). Classification of carbonate rocks according to depositional texture. 180-121, in W.E Hom, Ed., Classification of carbonate rocks, Tulsa, Okla. Amer. Asso. Petrol. Geol. 1.1. 108-121.
- Folk, R.L. (1959). Practical petrographic classification of limestone. Bull. Amer. Asso. Petrol. Geol. 43. 1-38.
- Folk, R.L. (1962). Petrography and origin of the Silurian Rochester and MacKenize shales, Morgan Country, West Virginia; Jour. Sedimentary Petrology, V.32, P.539-578.
- Wilson, J.L. (1975). Carbonate facies in geologic history, Springer –Verlag, Berlio, p.471.